

Addressing gender-specific needs in Europe's current and future transport systems

Actionable knowledge from the findings of the EU project DIAMOND

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CONTENTS

Executive Summary.....	3
Introduction	3
Review of Current Literature and examples of applied scenarios	4
DIAMOND Definition of Fairness.....	6
DIAMOND Definition of women	7
Research Questions asked in DIAMOND.....	8
Data Collection.....	8
Other project in line with recommendation from the DIAMOND project.....	9
Research Findings DIAMOND.....	12
Public Transport users.....	26
Autonomous driving.....	27
Bike-sharing.....	28
Women as Employees.....	28
Public Transport users.....	29
Autonomous Vehicles	30
Bike Sharing.....	30
Women as Employees.....	30
Possibilities for Change.....	32
RECOMMENDATIONS taking as a reference the maturity model.....	34
In Summary.....	38
APPENDIX 1.....	42
APPENDIX 2.....	43
APPENDIX 3.....	43
APPENDIX 4.....	44
APPENDIX 5.....	47
APPENDIX 6.....	47
References.....	51

Executive Summary

This White Paper considers key issues and actions for moving towards a fair, inclusive, and women-participated mobility and transport system. Within this context, the document will attempt to recommend concrete measures to enhance women's participation as users and employees to support the design of transport modes and access of infrastructure able to be more inclusive and informed also by women's need. The White Paper is informed by the main findings and recommendations of the EU Horizon 2020 funded DIAMOND project and other related projects.

Introduction

The DIAMOND project aimed to cover fairness and inclusion in line with factors effecting women as users of public transport, automated vehicles, bike-sharing and as employees in the transport sector. The project understands that when trying to create inclusiveness for women, it is essential to have an approach that does not see women as discriminated against simply because they have less participation. According to Friedman and Nissenbaum[i] (1996), a process is biased '[...] if it systematically and unfairly discriminates against certain individuals or groups of individuals in favour of others. A system discriminates unfairly if it denies an opportunity or a good, or if it assigns an undesirable outcome to an individual or a group of individuals on grounds that are unreasonable or inappropriate'. Yet 'unfair discrimination alone does not give rise to bias unless it occurs systematically' and 'systematic discrimination does not establish bias unless it is joined with an unfair outcome'. Hence, defining fairness in each of the Use Case considered in this project, from the philosophical perspective and in combination with application of computer science, will be key to automatically take action and support transport systems advance become more inclusive (DIAMOND proposal - Description of Action[ii]).

A key issue relevant to 'fairness' in the DIAMOND project is *equality*. Two ways in which equality impacts on fairness are: equality of opportunities and equality of outcomes.

In the context of the DIAMOND project, equality of opportunities can be seen to relate to such issues as accessibility to suitable transport services (or employment in transport). Such equal opportunity can be seen as a state of fairness in which people are treated similarly, unimpeded by prejudices or unnecessary distinctions or barriers, except when they can be explicitly justified (e.g., cheaper fares for young or low-income people, etc.). In other words, there should be fair and equal opportunity for people with a variety of different characteristics (e.g., mothers, older age, those in minority groups, etc.) to access a safe, secure, effective and efficient transport systems that meets their daily needs. With its roots in the wider concept of social justice, equality of opportunity supports the idea that opportunities should not be restricted for different groups of people. Substantive equality of opportunity (i.e., *substantive justice*) implies that a 'fair' system seeks to minimise not only explicit discrimination, but also indirect discrimination (Hail, Y., & McQuaid, R. (2021). The Concept of Fairness in Relation to Women Transport Users. *Sustainability*, 13(5)Sustainability 2021,(5), 2919; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13052919>), 2919).

For instance, those who have primary responsibilities for young children when travelling should have full access to services (e.g., when using pushchairs, etc.). This 'fair access' should be the case irrespective of the sex of the person responsible for the child, but in most cases, this would be a woman. Hence this particular barrier mainly (but not solely) affects women and under the umbrella of the equality of opportunity heading a 'fair' transport system would seek to remove the barrier. Although the focus of this project is fair access for women, 'fairness' applies to all people, but certain types of unfairness disproportionately affect people with certain characteristics, in particular women.

The DIAMOND project is particularly concerned with the female experience, and with different sub-groups such as age, childcare responsibilities, other caring responsibilities, income, socio-economic factors, locations, etc.), and how these characteristics disproportionately reduce real opportunities in regard to using or being employed in the transport sector. For example, the costs of train fares being similar across similar journeys or between groups, the planning of services, and the accessibility of services. However, there may be complicating factors where differences may be seen as being fair, such as off-peak pricing, elderly or family discount fares, etc. In these cases, the service may be seen as different (the same train journey during rush hour is not the same as during off-peak times; and biases for one group such as discounts for the elderly, may reflect (albeit not very effectively) ability to pay and so equality of opportunity can take account of the social economic and other circumstances of the people involved.

In relation to employment in the transport industry, all people should also have fair and equal opportunities to access all types (levels, occupations etc.) of employment and the relevant training and educational opportunities which would support their role and promotion in the industry. However, we can see from the actual employment patterns (outcomes) that this is usually not the case for many groups of women (e.g., those with dependent children, etc.). There are barriers, lack of support, etc. which mean women tend to be under-represented in many types and levels of jobs in the transport sector.

Fairness, therefore, should not reflect solely one characteristic (i.e., gender) but on a range of characteristics such as childcare responsibilities, age, income, socio-economic circumstances, ethnicity, and other characteristics present in anti-discrimination and human rights legislation.

^[1] from page 3- 2 Annex 1 Description of Action

Review of Current Literature and examples of applied scenarios

Fairness in transport has been based on the principles of treating people equally: no one suffering the costs or getting the benefits disproportionately and ensuring at least minimal levels of transport provision (Trinder et al, 1991). Justice and fairness have become increasingly important in sustainability and transport policy for decades, yet definition of fairness and how it should be incorporated into transport decision making and planning remains unclear (Verlinghieri and Schwanen, 2020; Linovski et al, 2018; Pereira, et al, 2017). The concept of fairness in a society varies over time and with circumstances alongside based on individual subjective reasoning and experiences, for this reason people's acceptance is vital in adopting or promoting sustainability across society (Eriksson, 2006). Hence, fairness for public transport users' play's a significant role in achieving a more environmentally and socially sustainable future.

Many women, due to socially constructed norms, experience transport differently. They have different mobilities, their perception and use of transport differs from that of men. On average they also have lower income than men (Crane, 2007; European Commission, 2018; Hudson, 2018), and less career progression (Hudson, 2018). These socially constructed functions and norms can be described as: care (for kids, elderly, etc.) (Crane, 2007; Hanson, 2010; McCarthy et al., 2017; European Commission, 2018), domestic duties (Crane, 2007; Hanson, 2010; European Commission, 2018), part-time work and/or staggered schedule (Crane, 2007). Moreover, due to their normatively constructed social role, women are viewed to embody movements or move through space which fails to accommodate strollers, shopping carts, those carrying children etc.

The 2018 Report on equality between women and men in the EU indicates that even with all the policies developed for a more equal European society, 73% of the Europeans affirm that women spend more time than men on housework and caring activities (European Commission, 2018). In Europe, women are more dependent than men on public transport networks. In France and Sweden, for example, men only use public transport for 10% of their trips, and two thirds of passengers on public transport networks are women (Duchène, 2011). However, it is worth mentioning that whilst women account for the majority of bus passengers, fewer women use it at night than men (Saunders, 2019).

Women have distinct safety/security needs and are often fearful of certain transit environments and frequently adjust their behaviour and travel patterns to avoid them (Loukaitou-Sideris, 2014). Safety needs to be treated with attention, and solutions should come from a holistic approach - better environment, better design, better interactions in the stations and in the area, rather than just a security approach: camera surveillance, grids, situational prevention, defensible spaces, all of which tends to create more anxiety than a feeling of safety (Blache, 2013). One aspect key to solve this situation is the obtention of disaggregated data, because in the root of the problem is the invisibility of women in the data sets as Caroline Criado-Pérez brilliantly explained in her book *Invisible Women: Exposing Data Bias in a World Designed for Men* (Criado-Pérez, 2019). Railway stations and connexion corridors to subway, bus, etc. can be a high cause of anxiety related to safety perception along with lack of comfort and accessibility. More adaptation of infrastructure and services to women need is a key issue (Duchène, 2011). Lowering the sense of anxiety is strongly related to urban design.

The increase of automation in vehicles is a reality, embedded in other social, economic and technological trends. And, although fully automated vehicles, still under development, will be a near future reality, the detail of their design, configuration and functionalities remains open. What we know so far is that traditionally in the automotive sector human centred design has been overshadowed by technology-led innovation (Saunders, 2019). This together with designs made for an 'average man' has raised serious safety issues for certain groups, notoriously women. The fact that women's needs and requirements are not properly addressed is not an exclusive situation of the automotive industry as (Criado-Pérez, 2019) explains brilliantly in her book *Invisible women: Exposing Data bias in a World Designed for Men. With new forms of big data, automated and micro-mobility changing the scene fast, leaders in mobility need a strong human-centred framework for navigating the technological evolutions coming from everywhere* (Saunders, 2019). And of course, this human-centred innovation has to be women inclusive.

The innovation within the automotive sector has created safer, cleaner, and more affordable vehicles, but progress has been mainly incremental (Anderson et al., 2014). One of the key elements of the innovation referring to autonomous vehicles is the introduction over time of increasing degrees of driver assistance. The need to organise the presence and combination of different assisting elements, from active safety systems, to driving support features and automated driving systems, has led to proposing different classification levels of automation according to the technological capabilities and the need of human involvement (Kyriakidis et al., 2015). Basically, the levels of vehicle automation range from driver-assist technologies (e.g. lane keeping, parking assist, etc.) to full vehicle automation, in which the vehicle is responsible for all critical safety functions (Olsen & Sweet, 2019).

Without going too much into detail is important to mention some aspects. From a geographical perspective there have been three main development hubs: (1) Europe (with known initiatives in UK, Germany and Italy), (2) US and (3) Japan. On other front, if we analyse the entities participating in this development, at first, they were mostly universities and research centres. Later, companies from inside and outside the automotive sector got involved too. From a technology point of view early efforts were highway-automation systems not really robots or driverless cars. Later the cars took the focus again. And now we have a blurred border zone as the vehicle gains intelligence and autonomy but at the same time increases the connection and communication to other vehicles (V2V) and also to the infrastructure (V2I). Several authors give their vision on the recent history of Autonomous Vehicles (Billington, 2018; Bishop, 2020; Bogost, 2014; Gammon, 2016; Nguyen, 2019).

Bike-sharing services is an innovative solution to the urban mobility challenges confronting urban dwellers (Goodman and Cheshire, 2014). It provides sustainable mobility means for urban trips that are deemed too far to walk but too close and complex for car/public transportation (Monisha, 2020). Notwithstanding, the popularity of cycling varies significantly between and within countries. What is common, however, is that cities all over the world have increasingly started to search and implement policies that would improve the modal share of cycling in transport (Handy, Wee and Kroesen, 2014). Like public transport, gender role is an important demographic variable that defines the mobility patterns in cycling and bike-sharing (Duchène, 2011; Ancaes, 2014; Goodman and Cheshire, 2014; Ricci, 2015; Li et al., 2015; Raux, Zoubir and Geyik, 2017; Gauvin et al., 2019; Winslow and Mont, 2019), yet gender-related barriers have received significantly less policy attention from policy-makers to bridge the gap between male and female users.

It is evident that women cycle less or use bicycle-sharing services less than men (Howland et al., 2017; McNeil et al., 2017a, 2018). Convenience, harassment or abuse by other road users, travelling with children or goods, cost, access and logistics, and knowledge and experience are the commonly cited barriers to cycling and bicycle-sharing schemes (BSS) use by women (Howland et al., 2017; McNeil, Dill, MacArthur and Broach, 2017b, 2017a; McNeil, Broach and Dill, 2018; Winslow and Mont, 2019; Wu et al., 2019). Suggestion's view developing a more inclusive BSS could plausibly attract a more

diverse representation of users while increasing the proportion of the underrepresented users such as females and persons from deprived neighbourhoods (Goodman and Cheshire, 2014; Winslow and Mont, 2019).

In the EU only 22 % of transport workers are women (European Commission, 2019). In all countries there are far fewer women working in transport-related jobs, whether in terms of road maintenance or access to the profession of bus or truck driver, which are seen as being 'men's work' (Duchène, 2011). For example, in 2017 in Spain, only 2.1% of women were employed in transport and logistics jobs, in contrast with 17.4% of commercial sector. One of the **obstacles** highlighted to explain the lack of women drivers is the question of working hours, especially in the case of women lorry drivers. Also, social norms in developing countries often prevent women from working in the transport sector. This is all the truer in the case of long-distance freight haulage. This sector provides many jobs from which women are barred (European Commission, 2019).

DIAMOND Definition of Fairness

A working definition of fairness for the DIAMOND project: a state in which people are treated similarly, unimpeded by prejudices or unnecessary distinctions or barriers, except they can be explicitly justified. Definition confines expatiated in Appendix(I). Applicable to DIAMOND's confines, fairness includes;

Capable of meeting required needs of people - in relation to people's job roles, flexible working, training etc. ability to travel in an appropriately designed transport system, meeting basic expectations and being environmentally sound.

Accessible - ability to access activities and services that people have reason to value; accessible to all groups also in terms of design and comfort provided, e.g., those with children, and in terms of fares and costs for those with lower income, including distribution of costs and benefits; all people can fairly access jobs for which they are suitable.

Safe and Secure - ability to travel or work safely and securely for all type of users) Under each Use Case factors are identified that are particularly important, or where there are significant gaps in research.

From this perspective inequitable or unfair transport policies and planning can have diverse and significant impacts on various groups at various times in relation to individuals' economic and social opportunities (Hail, Y., & McQuaid, R. (2021). The Concept of Fairness in Relation to Women Transport Users. *Sustainability*, 13(5), 2919; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13052919>), 2919.). Although the focus of this project is fair access for women, 'fairness' applies to all people, but certain types of unfairness disproportionately affect people with certain characteristics and/or normative social roles in particular, women (or groups such as women with young children).

DIAMOND Definition of women

The DIAMOND project has adopted a broad working definition of women for this project which is underpinned by the acknowledgement that gender (as opposed to only the biological sex class definition of women) is a social construction which changes over time and space (Guenther, Humbert and Kelan 2018). From this perspective gender is understood as the specific cultural meaning attached to the roles of men and women across and within societies. In the main gender looks to explain, in a rigid societal framework, the social norms, attitudes, and activities that each culture deems appropriate for one sex over the other at a specific moment in time (Koester 2015). Gender ideology therefore contains an innate power structure with reference to the public and private lives and experiences of women and girls' which impact on their role in the workplace, the academy, sports, and the arts (Scott 2018).

The power imbalance associated with societal gendered roles has led Koester (2015) to described gender as the 'most persistent cause, consequence and manifestation of power relations' (ibid 2015:1) globally. By providing a gendered distinction between men and women, Koester argues we are also identifying and labelling power and powerlessness. Therefore, when we explore the barriers and facilitators faced by women employed in and using public transport, we must also acknowledge the wider societal inequalities associated with their gender identity. Employing a gender focus in the project opposed to solely a biological sex class also allows us to collect data from biological women and those who self-identify as women and live their life as a woman. Recognising that there are different legal and other definitions and recognitions across the EU and elsewhere, the general definition of women adopted by the DIAMOND project is based on the broad concept of gender as a social construction which changes over time and space and allows us to examine the varying experiences of women.

Women are also not a homogeneous group, with each women's lived experience being shaped by, amongst other things, their social class, their ethnicity, and their geographical location as well as by age, childcaring responsibilities etc (Oliveira and Nisbet 2018). In order to capture the experiences of a wide selection of women for this project we have developed an intersectional approach to our analysis and designed our research instruments to record demographic data such as ethnic background, ability/disability, social class, and sexual identity/orientation. Therefore, whenever we talk about women in this study, it is done so with an understanding of the complexity of women's multiple social identities.

Research Questions asked in DIAMOND

Public Transport, Bike-Sharing and Autonomous vehicles

- Q1_What are the **key factors** affecting women's travel choices?
- Q2_How **relevant** are they in discriminating between different transport modalities?

Employees in public transport

- Q3_How different **job characteristics**, and/or contextual factors, in the transport sectors may affect gender balance and or female employability in different areas?
- Q4_What are the **key factors** influencing career choices for women in different groups and areas in relation to working in transport?

Data Collection

Figure 1: Diagram of method process (Appendix 2)

Type of Data collected

The main objective of the DIAMOND project was to turn data into reliable and actionable knowledge for supporting the inclusion of women in transport systems as both users and employees. The research focus was divided into four areas;

- Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways)
- Autonomous Passenger Car
- Vehicle (Bike) Sharing Fleet Management
- Employment of Women in Rail Industry and Freight/CSR Protocols.

In order to answer the research questions as set out above the project consortium collected heterogeneous and disaggregated data regarding women's needs in the transport sector, as users and employees.

The gathered data sets were divided into three main categories:

Thematic Analysis:

- Literature review
- Focus group discussions
- Semi-structured interviews

Service and Employers Provision Data:

- Structured data regarding the operation of transport services and job holders of the sector
- Observations regarding relevant features of transportation settings and emotional responses to autonomous vehicles
- Users and Employees' Satisfaction Index questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users of the services and job conditions and employability

Social media data from Twitter regarding geospatial/ time-based information and the opinion of the end-users of the services

Users and Employees' Perception Data:

- DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires regarding the Fairness Characteristics

Refer to appendix 3 for further information

Other projects in line with recommendation from the DIAMOND project

The International Transport Forum (ITF) is an intergovernmental organisation with over 62 member countries which is used to develop transport policy. In its report 'Transport Innovation for Sustainable Development A Gender Perspective' (February 2021), ITF discussed topics involving gender equality, such as is shared mobility innovative enough for gender needs, designing transport networks with women's mobility needs in mind and overcoming barriers to women's employment in transport.

The report stated that currently women fill only 22% of jobs within the transport sector. It is one of the EU economy's most male-dominated sectors, this is possibly because of persisting stereotypes. Women in Europe are more likely to make environmentally friendly choices, such as limiting their car use, and are more positive towards car-use reduction actions, including improving and expanding public transport. Yet current studies suggest their needs are less likely to be considered during the design of transport systems and are more likely to be affected by transport poverty.

Nearly 40% of public transport journeys throughout the world are mobility of care journeys. These include visits to health centres, escorting dependents, for shopping and to carry out other errands. While work related journeys account for not even 20%. Women make up 80% of people in charge of mobility of care and most of these women use sustainable modes either walking or using public transport. Despite this currently transport planning is typically focused on commuting to and from work but these routes are often not the easiest routes for mobility of care. Mobility of care usually consists of more frequent, local and shorter trips and is irregular in time (no peak/ off-peak) and space (not only from residential to the city centre). Therefore, future transport planning needs to take care of mobility journeys into account.

One of the European Union's core values is gender equality. The European commission committed to systematically including a gender perspective in all stages of policy design in all areas. However, women only represent seventeen percent of workers in information and communication technology and only thirty six percent of science, technology, engineering and mathematics graduates. With this digital gap continuing to expand the number of female workers in transport risks diminishing further. Policies need to help in addressing the gender and technology inequality and give transport workers the right to decent work in this fast-changing world. This starts with giving access to education and proper training. More broadly gendered public policies are required to deal with women's unequal position in the economy. On an even bigger level and global scale, in March of 2019 the International Transport Workers' Federation and the International Association of Public Transport signed an agreement to strengthen women's employment in the public transport sector.

The recommendations covered nine main areas:

- Working culture and gender stereotypes
- Recruitment
- Work environment and design
- Facilities (including sanitation)
- Health and safety at work
- Work/life balance
- Training
- Pay equality
- Corporate policy

Transport Infrastructure Ireland carried out a project intitled 'Travelling in a Woman's Shoes' (July 2020) which looked at understanding women's travel needs in Ireland to inform the future of sustainable transport policy and design. It aimed to understand why women make the mobility choices they do and what their daily aspirations and challenges were. This study analysed available data, other studies from Ireland and relevant global literature before carrying out an ethnographic study. The ethnographic methodology (although not often used in transport research) allowed for a better understanding of the realities of what women deal with daily, introduced a diversity of perspectives and added to the data that look at gender in travel behaviour. As women were given the opportunity to tell their stories feelings such as stress, fear and joy were captured, which are not easily recorded but are definite motivators of transport behaviour while a wide range of infrastructure, technological and social issues were also revealed. This data gives a clear view of what is going on beyond the existing measures, performance indicators and statistical data. Decision makers cannot ignore the impact of transport and land-use policies in real context and how this data may hold the key to sustainable future solutions.

From the point of view of Autonomous Vehicles the following projects should be mention. Prometheus for being the first important initiative in AVs in Europe. SUaaVe because we have crossed some results and gained knowledge. Connected Automated Driving because it is the reference network in Europe for CAV.

The Eureka **PROMOTHEUS** project (**PRO**gramme for a **E**uropean **T**raffic of **H**ighest **E**fficiency and **U**nprecedented **S**afety, 1987–1995) is the largest **R&D project** ever in the field of **driverless cars**. It received 749 millions of euros in funding from the pan-European research organization Eureka, and defined the state of the art of **autonomous** vehicles. Numerous academic organizations and car manufacturers participated in this project.

The contribution of Ernts Dickmanns (DELCKER, 2018), and his team at Bundeswehr Universität München, was beyond doubt more than noteworthy. In 1994 their twin vehicles VaMP and VITA-2 drove more than one thousand kilometres on a Paris multi-lane highway in standard heavy traffic at speeds up to 130 km/h. The achievements represented a real breakthrough: driving in free lanes, convoy driving, automatic tracking of other vehicles, and lane changes left and right with autonomous passing of other cars. In 1995, a re-engineered autonomous S-Class Mercedes, took 1000-mile trip from Munich in Bavaria to Copenhagen in Denmark and back, using saccadic computer vision and transputers to react in real time. The robot achieved speeds exceeding 175 km/h on the German Autobahn. Despite being a research system without emphasis on long distance reliability, it drove up to 158km without any human intervention.

SUaaVE project coordinated by IBV (grant agreement N° 814999) is working on the development of a psychological acceptability model with the intention to explain public acceptability of connected autonomous vehicle (CAV) among different types of user groups within the EU, led by RUG University.

In SUaaVE, with the goal of collecting data from European population to feed the acceptability model, a large-scale survey was conducted in April 2020. In this survey, all potential psychological factors influencing acceptability of CAV were measured to determine their significance and strength.

The results of this action are included in SUaaVE Public deliverable 1.2. 'Model and guidelines depicting key psychological factors that explain and promote public acceptability of CAV among different user groups'.

The database obtained in SUaaVE large survey has a high value in the exploration of gender differences in CAV acceptance. For this reason, a collaboration between RUG University (SUaaVE partner) and IBV (leader of autonomous vehicle use case in DIAMOND) was performed to make a complementary analysis of this data base to identify women priorities to enhance in CAV perception for boosting women acceptability of CAVs.

Connected Automated Driving. It is the reference European network on CAV. It was developed as part of the horizon 2020 Action ARCADE (**A**liance **R**esearch & **I**nnovation for **C**onected and **A**utomated **D**riving in **E**urope). This Knowledge Base gathers the scattered information among a broad network of CAD stakeholders to establish a common baseline of CAD knowledge and provide a platform for a broad exchange of knowledge. It has become the one-stop shop for data, knowledge and experiences on CAD in Europe and beyond.

The Knowledge Base is ever-evolving and growing with the existing body of knowledge in the field. It promotes the sharing of knowledge, data and experiences for the development of connected and automated driving.

DIAMOND Research Findings

Research Question regarding the key factors affecting women's travel choices

The key factors affecting women's choices in relation to them as users of transport. From data principally collected in Europe the finding is - Majorly **Safety & security** clustered by - 'Police force, security or staff personnel' + 'Visibility of the surrounding area of the station'. And then issues of **Accessibility of the service** - 'Operational hours & intervals' + 'Travel & Wayfinding information provision' + 'Service availability and efficiency.'

Overall, findings show;

- Safety and security
- Costs
- Facilities for infant feeding and changing.

- Operational hours and frequency of public service
- For AV's specifically simultaneity, trust in technology

Research Question regarding relevance of factors affecting women travel choice and how they discriminate between different transport modalities

In discriminating between different transport modalities results suggest that in the main the high-level factors are similar across all transport modes, and that women are particularly interested and focused on safety and security, costs, frequency, accessibility, availability, which should be understood in the context of the family and caring responsibilities that women negotiate with in their daily routines.

Railways public transport

- Adequate personal space, layout of seating and appropriate ventilation and air conditioning
- Walking time from stations to the points of interest
- Intermodal options and connections. Including integration with alternative shared mobility services (e.g. bike, scooter and car sharing)
- Safety and harassment reporting points
- Visibility of the surrounding area
- Availability of appropriate services/facilities within the transport infrastructure (seating area, bar, pharmacy, ATMs...)
- Reliability of the service modes available in terms of time, price and security

Autonomous driving

- Perception of boredom vs joy inside the autonomous vehicle
- Degree of interaction between passengers
- Perception of using a vehicle that contributes to reducing the ecological impact and building a sustainable society
- Importance of controlling the speed of the vehicle
- Be able to perform simultaneous tasks while the AVs drives in a comfortable environment

- Importance to transmit to the potential users that the AVs is safe when driving in bad weather conditions to increase their trust in the technology
- Importance of allowing the user select sportive driving mode and other driving preferences that sets how the vehicle will behave while driving
- Consider and optimise the well-being of other road users in determining vehicle behaviour
- Health: people feeling (e.g. calm, stressed) when driving without steering wheel

Bike-sharing

- Campaign to raise awareness on the benefits of cycling
- Facilities at the docking stations (rain poncho, changing rooms and enough docking points)
- Avoid hilly terrain in the new cycle lanes
- Weather cycle-friendly infrastructure
- Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo
- Safe cycle routes (for children and to attract more people)
- Lowering the speed of other vehicles in shared lanes
- Safety and security – provision of safety equipment and personal safety, Misuse of docking points and of bikes
- Fear of cycling in the traffic / Traffic safety and aggressive driving
- Unavailability of bikes at the station
- Unavailability of docking points to return bikes after trip
- Distant of docking stations from user
- Inadequate and unsafe cycle infrastructure

For each individual mode the research shows the relevance of factors affecting women travel choice and how they discriminate between different transport modalities, overall analysis suggests:

- Safety and security
- sense of place
- Comfort
- Phycological impact
- reliance on private vehicles
- Convenience
- Perception
- Reference or mind set
- Design option
- Environments

Research Question regarding relevance of factors affecting women travel choice and how they discriminate between different transport modalities

In discriminating between different transport modalities results suggest that in the main the high-level factors are similar across all transport modes, and that women are particularly interested and focused on safety and security, costs, frequency, accessibility, availability, which should be understood in the context of the family and caring responsibilities that women negotiate with in their daily routines.

All these key factors listed above which give an answer to Q1 were weighted and hierarchized in the DIAMOND project with the aim to figure out the relevance of each of these factors in the travel choice by women per each use case.

This relevance of factors was calculated by AHP and BN and it was based on the preferences showed in the DAD survey, UESI satisfaction surveys, observation checklists and structured data sets as stated in the data collection section (see more details in Molero et al. 2021).

The relevance of each of these key factors mentioned before are depicted in a sectorial graph in Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3 for railways public transport, autonomous vehicles and bicycle sharing, respectively.

Figure 1. Sectorial graph with the distribution of the relevance between the key factors for the railway stations

Figure 2. Sectorial graph with the distribution of the relevance between the top 10 factors for autonomous vehicles

Figure 3. Sectorial graph with the distribution of the relevance between the top 10 factors for bike sharing

Research Question regarding how different job characteristics, and/or contextual factors, in the transport sectors may affect gender balance and or female employability in different areas

The job characteristics and contextual factors identified by the data as being important in terms of affecting gender balance and female employability in different areas in the transport sector were

- Job Segregation
- Demand Factors
- Policy and Legal
- Female Facilities
- HR Policies
- Terms and Conditions
- Flexible Working
- Training Provision

- Safety and Security
- Negative Attitude of Colleagues
- Caring/Parenting Responsibilities
- Skills
- Educational Attainment

In a higher level of concretion, DIAMOND figured out that job characteristics and contextual factors that may affect gender balance and female employability by making easier to business and transport organizations to access all kind of candidates are the next:

- Gender equality communication policies - 49%
- Gender pay equality per each job position –26%
- Equality gender in promotions and recruitments – 25%

Figure 2 depicts the relevance about how much each of these factors affects the gender balance and female employability obtained from the analysis:

Figure 4. Sectorial graph with the distribution of the relevance between the key factors for the gender balance in the employability

Research Question regarding the key factors influencing career choices for women in different groups and areas in relation to working in transport

The key factors identified by the data as being important in relation to women's career choices in the transport sector were

- Job Segregation
- Demand Factors – recruitment and retainment
- Policy and Legal – employment policies
- Female facilities
- HR Policies – training and promotion
- Terms and Conditions – equal pay, shift patterns
- Flexible Working
- Safety and Security – Personal Protection Equipment (PPE) etc.

- Negative attitude of colleagues
- Caring and parenting responsibilities
- Educational Attainment
- Measures to enhance women job hiring
- The adaption of training modules to the required new skills and opportunities

Moreover, DIAMOND figured out that 'family-friendly policies, such as opportunities to reduce working time and change shifts, especially for those with small children', is a key factor influencing on the career choices for women, and to work in the transport sector (Molero et al. 2021).

Job Characteristics

Figure: Measure of job characteristics in the Irish organisation

Job Characteristics

Figure: Measure of job characteristics in the Spanish organisation

Satisfaction

Figure: Overall Job satisfaction in Irish organisation

Satisfaction

Figure: Overall Job satisfaction in Spanish organisation

Recommendations made by participants to encourage more women employees in the transport sector:

- Flexible working available for men and women
- More women in senior roles
- When recruiting take 5 male and 5 female for each role
- Input at school level to attract young girls and women to STEM

As evidenced above the research data suggests job segregation and lack of flexible working are among the biggest factors impacting gender balance and female employability in the sector. Respondents made recommendations to address these issues.

Regarding job segregation, to address the commonly reported theme that 'you can't be what you can't see' practices such as 'women in transport days', specific women in transport groups and educational events were cited as examples of support received that positively impact upon women employees and a more equal gender balance in the industry. Also, respondents noted the importance of education in schools, colleges and universities regarding the transport sector as a potential employer. Recommendations were also made to enhance flexible working across all job types in the sector.

'I think there are still some professions where women think 'I wouldn't be able to do that'. And when they suddenly see someone in a job ad and they see a woman doing it it's a bit, what's that saying, you can't be what you can't see. We need to see a lot more women in a lot more diverse roles and look at them and think 'oh I can relate to that, maybe I could do that too, that looks like fun or interesting or challenging'.

Sarah F, Director, UK

'...for engineering, I think we need to go to the to the source. So, schools and colleges so that we get the fresh talent.'

Samantha F, Director, UK

'I think there are still some professions where women think 'I wouldn't be able to do that'. And when they suddenly see someone in a job ad and they see a woman doing it it's a bit, what's that saying, you can't be what you can't see. We need to see a lot more women in a lot more diverse roles and look at them and think 'oh I can relate to that, maybe I could do that too, that looks like fun or interesting or challenging'.

Sarah F, Director, UK

'They [women] are not aware at all, it's not all just about dirty truck driving, the trucks now are really like, they are all IT, they have telematics and electronics. Our industry really needs to be pushing women forwards. The trade bodies should also be putting women forward, they are trying but it needs more than a picture of a woman in a high viz and hard hat. Women cannot do this by ourselves we need the help of men; men need to understand the importance of females in the workplace.'

Louise F, Truck Director, UK

Recommendations were also made to enhance flexible working across all job types in the sector:

‘We have also introduced things like flexible working, and we introduced it a long time before COVID came and I am delighted to say that it enabled our business to do something amazing and keep going right from the start of lock down because all of our people were able to do flexible working. But we don’t just have flexible working in the office, we have worked with ASLEF (train drivers union) to make sure we have job share for our train drivers. Job share is available for our train drivers.’

Naomi F, Rail Director, UK

And as this director pointed out, ‘traditional arrangements’ could be altered by ‘thinking differently’ about flexibility for all roles:

‘There is not that thinking outside of the box (currently), well you know that could be done by two people it could be terms time it could be annualized hours, people are not thinking wider and that is why, you know it goes back to the traditional arrangements. I am seeing clients doing a complete U turn now and its whether that will happen with operational jobs. It is happening with office jobs. It’s how, you know, maybe could a job be done by one person doing two days and another three days, its thinking differently about things.’

Frances F, Rail Director, UK

Development of online Bayesian Belief Networks for the use cases to allow simulation of fairness parameters and their impact on user satisfaction.

The data and results obtained from the UESI and from the observations were used to set up an online version of the Bayesian networks using the Hugin Platform to allow users to connect online and access the model to verify how each fairness characteristics in each use case impacted the likelihood of fuser satisfaction for different categories of users (considering demographic characteristics on each use case).

I. Use Case I model.

The input data for the model was obtained from questionnaires applied on a wide range of population from Poland and Spain. The questionnaires covered indicators on station properties (e.g., platform and concourse), social and demographic information. The complete data was split into training and test sets (in a ratio of 3:1). The training data was used to define the parameters of the Bayesian Network model by implementing learning algorithms. Once the model was completely defined, the test data set was used to assess the performance of the model. The target variable was defined as Travel Satisfaction. This variable provides information on the contentment level of users using the travel network in different countries. One of the challenges of this study was the limited size of dataset. In response to this, fixed structure models such as the Naïve Bayes Model were defined. This model consists in a finite number of feature variables that depend on a single node known as the class variable (Jensen et al 2007). In addition, reduced state space using expert knowledge, hierarchical model to reflect groups of nodes were determined.

The steps in the model development are the following:

1. Factor analysis on indicators from questionnaire. Produced factors 0 – 3 – named using expert knowledge
 - a. Certain indicators of special interest for the analysis and use of the model were included in the model despite being removed by the feature selection (e.g., sex)
2. Feature selection on station, social and demographic indicators using an inclusive wrapper approach (FI-score used) assuming a naïve Bayes model structure and training data to score
 - a. Considered the hidden nodes for each factor group independently (due to complete data)
 - b. Used the Expectation-Maximization algorithm with AIC as model score to identify the number of states of the hidden node. The search started from 2 states up to 10 states (if 10 states produced the highest score, the limit was increase to 15)
 - c. The model producing the highest AIC score was selected
3. Introduced layer of hidden nodes between target and each group of factors (seven groups)
4. The final model structure was created by combining the models for each factor group into a single structure

Figure: Final bayesian network model structure was created by combining the models for each factor group into a single structure

The Value of information on each factor captures the value of being able to know each factor condition even before making a travel satisfaction prediction. The results show the value of information of each of the selected factor variables relative to the Travel Satisfaction before the decision. There is one bar for each information variable labelled with their corresponding name. The size of the bar is proportional to a factor of the maximum expected utility of the decision.

Figure: Value of information of hidden nodes representing each factor.

The performance of the final model was assessed on the test dataset using Area Under the Curve. The model performance was compared with the performance of the naïve Bayes model. Other model structures were considered but found to produce a lower AUC score.

The BBN model for predicting travel satisfaction has been implemented in an online platform open to the public²². The platform allows visualising the graph of the network as a way to represent the dependencies of the variables involved in the model. Also, a number of ‘what-if’ scenarios can be defined to assess the impact of factors such as demographics, station status or questionnaire, in the Travel satisfaction. This can be done by selecting the parameters for each factor through the interactive menus.

2. Use Case II model.

This model focuses on the autonomous vehicles Acceptance among general population. The input data was collected through a series of questionnaires applied on a diverse range of population going from people with different ages to different vehicle needs. One of the challenges encountered during this study is related to the missing factor analysis. For this reason, a simple Naïve Bayes Model with no hidden nodes was defined. This approach allowed to also overcome the problem related to the limited size of dataset. The defined model was defined including only variables with value of information higher than 0.005.

Figure: Overview of the Naïve Bayes network built for Use case II limited UESI data set.

In this model the Value of information for each factor captures the value of being able to know each element condition before making a prediction on the Acceptance variable.

Figure: Value of information for Autonomous vehicle acceptance model.

4. Use Case IV model.

This network represents the likelihood of users being satisfied with inclusiveness

Figure: Bayesian network on organisation inclusive satisfaction.

Following the design thinking sessions, the work for task 5.1 has continued with an analysis of the outcomes of these sessions, to refine customer journey mapping, understand what

Figure: Value of information of organisation inclusive satisfaction model.

The Model performance, in terms of Area under the Curve is reported in the Figure below.

Figure: Model performance.

An online version of the predictive model for organizational inclusive satisfaction can be found on the website²⁵. A capture of the website is shown below.

Recommendations on making transport use and employment more appropriate and friendly for women

At least one recommendation per each of key factors identified in the DIAMOND research findings (section 8) was generated and validated by an interdisciplinary panel with gender experts inside and outside the project consortium.

Hereafter the priority recommendations per each of the use cases are indicated:

Public Transport users

Goal: Increase the number of women using railways and public transport in peak hours and off-peak hours.

Priority recommendations: The next are priority recommendations addressing key factors to improve the use of the railways system and public transport by women.

- Staff available to provide assistance in case someone feels others are intruding into their personal space or harassing them
- Improve the seating design fulfilling needs of pregnant women, disable people and people with toddlers
- Improve the cross ventilation and air-conditioned adapting it to different seasons

- Give information to users indicating access to near key points (e.g. walking time, appropriate station exit indications)
- Connection paths and access points should be adapted to all users (e.g. people with reduced mobility, those travelling with children or dependents, visually impaired people). For example adapting the station access with ramps, escalators and lifts
- Improve response time of security personnel to any incident
- Increase lightning in the stations and their surroundings
- Display the services available in the station (e.g. seating area, bar, pharmacy, ATMs...)
- Improve the coordination between the timetables of the different transport modes available in the stations
- Introduce special points/docks of shared mobility in each station

To achieve a high impact^[1] on the achievement of the goal, railways and public transport service providers should implement the next measures, which demonstrated to affect drastically the satisfaction of all the key factors by women (Deliverable 7.3 DIAMOND):

- Display the services available in the station (e.g. seating area, bar, pharmacy, ATMs...)
- Improve response time of security personnel to any incident
- Increase lightning in the stations and their surroundings

Autonomous driving

Goal: Increase the acceptance level of autonomous driving by women.

Priority recommendations: The next are priority recommendations addressing key factors to improve the acceptance of autonomous vehicles by women.

- The design of the interior of the vehicle (e.g. seats, auxiliary surfaces, electronic facilities) should provide the comfort needed to perform non-driving related tasks such as work, as well as allow an easy reconfiguration to changing needs
- Design of the interior should give the possibility of a relax atmosphere (lighting condition, thermal comfort, music...)
- Allow the user select the degree of interaction with other passengers, defining private and/or shared areas
- To include ecological indicators in the information given by the car to the user through the human machine interface to allow him/her consult the environmental impact of his/her travels
- To include an automated system that controls the speed of the car for a comfortable travel experience
- Implement dissemination and promotional campaigns about AVs safety mechanisms in the case of bad weather in order to increase the trust in AVs technology
- Give information to the user related to the advantages and disadvantages of activating the sportive driving mode
- Give information/training to the users about the social benefits of the various driving parameters in order to facilitate them their interaction with the system and take decisions on adjustable automatic driving parameters
- Implement promotional campaigns to increase public awareness about benefits of automated driving versus manual/conventional cars

Designers and manufacturers of autonomous vehicles should seriously consider the next recommendations which showed a high impact on the acceptability of the autonomous driving by women (Deliverable 7.3 DIAMOND):

- To include an automated system that controls the speed of the car for a comfortable travel experience
- Allow the user to select the degree of interaction with other passengers, defining private and/or shared areas
- Give information to the user related to the advantages and disadvantages of activating the sportive driving mode

Note 1 Impact is based on the Effectiveness about how the implementation of each recommendation will affect the improvement of all Key factors (Top10 Factors) and also based on the cost of implementing this recommendation (Efficiency). This was estimated through a Bayesian Network analysis for the Effectiveness calculation and expert knowledge for the estimation of the costs. See D7.3 of DIAMOND for more details.

Bike-sharing

Goal: Increase the number of women using bike-sharing

Priority recommendations: The next are priority recommendations addressing key factors to improve the use of bike sharing services by women

- Inclusive promotional campaigns aimed at all the public and with special focus on specific social groups such as disabled people
- Availability of rain ponchos and other accessories at the stations to be used in rainy days
- Availability of electric bikes at every docking stations
- Use of special pavements to avoid slipping on rainy days
- Changing rooms for women

- Provide special bikes with child seats or baskets to facilitate traveling with children or after shopping
- Provide special cycle routes that were safe for children going to school
- Increase the number of docking points to guarantee the availability of bikes
- Separated cycle lanes free from vehicular traffic
- Suggest alternative routes to cyclists avoiding high speed roads

Next recommendations were those with the highest impact on the achievement of the goal by increasing the satisfaction of key factors by women.

- Ensure that all bikes have well-functioning safety lights and brakes
- Availability of electric bikes at every docking stations
- Suggest alternative routes to cyclists avoiding high speed roads

Women as Employees

Goal: Increase the on-site and off-site employment for women

Priority recommendations: The next are priority recommendations to improve the gender balance and female employability by making easier to business and transport organizations to access all kind of candidates.

- Gender neutral employment advertisements
- Flexibility with women in the maternity period to avoid glass ceilings in their professional development process
- Equity plans
- All roles/vacancies are open and available for both men and women

From these, next ones showed a high impact on the gender balance in the employment in the transport sector:

- Flexibility with women in the maternity period to avoid glass ceilings in their professional development process

- Gender neutral employment advertisements

On the other hand,

- Provide the option for working from home, teleworking or remote working is a priority recommendation to improve the career choice for women to work in the transport sector by making it more attractive for them

For information about possible future potential see Appendix 4

Profiles of Women that were highlighting issues for them in relation to some characteristics of public transport

In general, it could be said that living environment, **travelling with dependents, disability and previous discrimination suffered in transport** are the socio-demographic characteristics that seems to be more unsatisfied with the current railways and public transport system.

Autonomous Vehicles

Nonspecific profile for women showed significant differences, so, it could not be highlighted any specific group of women as the most unsatisfied with the autonomous vehicles.

Public Transport users

Table 1 indicates the profiles of women that were less satisfied with those aspects in their experience as user of railways transport system.

Key Factor	Profiles of Women
Adequate personal space, layout of seating and appropriate ventilation and air conditioning.	Women who have ever felt discriminated in transport
Walking time from stations to the points of interest.	Women travelling with dependents (elderly, children...)
	Women without disabilities
Intermodal options and connections. Including integration with alternative shared mobility services (e.g. bike, scooter and car sharing).	Women living in suburban areas
	Women living in rural areas
Safety and harassment reporting points	Women travelling with dependents (elderly, children...)
	Women living in rural areas
Visibility of the surrounding area	Women travelling with dependents (elderly, children...)
	Women living in rural areas
Availability of appropriate services/facilities within the transport infrastructure (seating area, bar, pharmacy,ATMs...).	Women travelling with dependents (elderly, children...)
	Women not travelling with dependents (elderly, children...)
Reliability of the service modes available in terms of time, price and security	Women not travelling with dependents (elderly, children...)

Table 1. Profiles of women more unsatisfied with the most relevant factors in transport users

Bike Sharing

Table 2 indicates the women that were less satisfied with some aspects of the bike sharing services.

Key Factor	Women profiles most unsatisfied
Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo	Women travelling with dependents (elderly, children...) Women with disability
Lowering the speed of other vehicles in shared lanes	Women who has ever felt discriminated in transport

Table 2. Profiles of women more unsatisfied with the most relevant factors in bike sharing

Women as Employees

The research data suggested that **there is job segregation within the transport system** and that it does **impact gender balance and female employability**. The job segregation, according to some interviewees, has come from historical or more traditional ideas of 'men's jobs' and 'women's jobs'. Across the sector the dominance of male employees was evident.

In order to address the issue of gender balance some companies were involved in attending schools, universities, colleges and job fairs to promote female employment in their transport company. This was to provide more of an **awareness and education around jobs in the transport sector**. Many interviewees suggested that more education and communication around the roles available within the transport sector and their suitability for women is necessary to encourage an increase in the number of women in transport job roles. Many pointed out examples of women in transport groups that support and positively impact women employees and help promote a more gender-balanced industry.

When looking at the gender balance and female employability with regard to vacancy characteristics the interviewees suggested shift work, working hours and opportunity for progressions as hindrance. While interviewees indicated that selection preferences, **recruitment and selection procedures** and discrimination all play a role in gender balance. While in regards to legal factors or policy the research data noted that they should in theory promote fairness in the workplace but actually are just a 'tick box' action.

The research also highlighted that **appropriate female facilities were lacking** meaning the working environment was discriminatory for women. The reason behind this lack in facilities was deemed to be as a result of the industries job segregation. The data did suggest also that many interviewees **experienced sexism and discrimination at work**.

In general across the sector and in the different locations organisations did not specifically target women for employment opportunities, as they did not want that in itself to be discriminatory and wanted the right person to get the job regardless of gender. However, organisations did have strategies such as diversity targets and equality plans. Many interviewees stated that their company does actively seek to retain their employees. The data disclosed many points in terms of training provision and gender balance. Generally there is equality of access to training that is usually paid for by the employer and there is often training designed specifically for women.

Fairness in the transport industry according to many of the interviewees is about flexibility, e.g. flexible working hours, however the data suggests that a lot of jobs in the transport industry would not be compatible with that type of flexibility. A lot of the interviewees also agreed that many roles require shift work and unsociable working hours, while this may not impact those who do not have children it greatly impacts those who do. While it was agreed that it would be discriminatory to suggest that women should provide the majority of childcare the interviewees recognised that the reality is that they often do. The evidence from the research data did indicate that caring/parenting responsibilities impact upon gender balance and women's employability in the transport industry.

The research data on FC skills in terms of gender balance or female employment did not provide many insights. Generally the data indicated that **specialist skills or educational level impacts the level or role undertaken by women** but a lot of the front line or operational roles are a learned skill within the organisation and women apprentices numbers are low. The interviews and focus group discussions found no data on the FCs of health status and wellbeing, economic deprivation residential location/work distance transport access to work place or for individual characteristics, such as adaptability, attitude to work in terms of adaptability and attitude to work.

In terms of increasing the participation of women employed in the transport system a key factor is the **concept of job segregation**, i.e. jobs for only men or only women. Across all the interviews the industry appeared to be still viewed and experienced as a male dominated industry. Three main themes emerged when discussing understanding of why girls and women are still underrepresented. They were that they were attracting women to the industry, recruitment processes, and processes put in place to retain women employees, all falling under FC demand factors. It was noted that **many women and young girls are not aware of the variety of roles within the transport sector and that more effort is needed to engage them**. However, during discussion in focus groups and interviews targeted recruitment of female employees was regarded as adding 'a target' to the backs of women.

A factor that was seen to impact in female career choices was having **female role models or mentors in the workplace**, some interviewees in senior roles agreed and claimed that they believed it was their responsibility to support any women who might want to follow in their footsteps.

The question 'Are current employment practices in your country fair for women?' was asked to determine the impact of employment policies and law across different partner states (Ireland, UK, Poland and Spain). The responses indicated that while there are many policies in place currently they are not utilised consistently across all organisations and that these policies are often developed by business men or lawyers who do not fully understand the experiences of women on the frontline, with the majority of responses declaring that more needs to be done.

Lack of female facilities and was one of the largest findings that emerged from the data to impact women's career choices in the transport industry. Many interviewees highlighted that there was a lack of space for women, they had to share a toilet with men or use the disabled toilets which in turn impacts the access of disabled people to their toilets.

In terms of equality of opportunity for women to access training provision, there was no difference seen compared to men. In terms of railways and road haulage, all drivers must legally have the same training in order to be employed.

The data related to the FC 'terms and conditions' suggested that across countries and transport organisations was equal pay not a key factor as it tended to be covered by legislation, meaning women and men are paid the same for the same job. However under this FC caring or parenting responsibilities was seen as a key factor for women's career choices. Flexible working hours and their provision was seen across all employment FCs.

Data from the **safety and security theme** included the provision of PPE designed for women and not unisex, other provisions that arose were lone working and training in protection and awareness. From the data it is seen that the majority of transport organisations are still providing unisex PPE (as regarded by them), which some frontline interviewees described as 'designed for men'.

The **perceived reaction of male colleagues to having women alongside them in the transport sector** can also be an important factor in women's career choices. Many interviewees working across the transport sector reported this, frontline managers, senior managers and directors supporting the idea that negative male attitudes towards women employees can still be found, even in the board rooms of the transport sector.

The **low numbers of women in STEM or technical subjects** that undermine many transport sector roles has an impact on educational attainment as a factor for women when considering a career in the transport sector. Many Organisations stated that in order to address this they now have a presence at **open days or career days in schools and colleges to encourage young girls to enter into the sector**.

The focus groups and interviews saw no data sets emerge from the FCs economic deprivation, transport access to work place, health status and wellbeing and effects of demographics (age ethnicity etc.). They also weren't seen in terms of adaptability and attitude to work but there are themes that emerged based on flexibility of working location and hours and the impact of shift work.

The findings that emerged from the data that were not before accounted for in the FCs that influence women's choice of career included the individual personality or characteristics that a woman may possess (Leva et al. 2021).

Possibilities for Change

In regards to women's employment in the transport sector and the factors that influence women's career choices in respect to employment the interviewees did acknowledge that there was a need for change in order to support women as employees in the sector. These changes will also help to encourage more women to join the sector.

Specific profiles for women showed significant differences on some of the key factors for various issues. The specific profiles of women reported less occurrence or frequency of the below statements, see Table 3.

Women Profile that rated less frequency of Key Factors/ less satisfied	Key Factor
Women who are parents/have children	In my community/country there is currently an equal balance between genders across occupations, levels and jobs in transport.
Women with long term chronic illness or disabilities	Overall how satisfied are you with the way your personal circumstances and needs are met in your workplace?
Women who having caring responsibilities outside work/Carers	My company's terms and conditions support maternity leave
My training and development needs are met as much as other people in my organisation	Women who having caring responsibilities outside work/Carers
In my community/country there is currently an equal balance between genders across occupations, levels and jobs in transport.	Women from Suburban and Rural (borderline p = .049)
I require working times that make it possible to accommodate work and family commitments (extended hours, variable start/ finish times, shiftwork etc.	Women of minority ethnicity
In my environment I feel the need for role models	Women without children
My company's terms and conditions support employees in their caring role, i.e., family friendly policies	Younger women
My company offers flexible Working Hours e.g. Teleworking / Working from home arrangements to all employees	Women of minority ethnicity
In my workplace I regularly need to exceed my working hours	Women with secondary to degree level education
I require support in my workplace for dealing with chronic/long-term health conditions of those I care for	Women on income of E11-22,999, E31-40,999
My training and development needs are met as much as other people in my organisation	Women travelling with dependents
In my company there is prevention of dismissal or demotion during and after maternity periods	Women with no education or only primary education
Overall how satisfied are you with the way your socio-economic needs have been supported in your workplace?	Women who having caring responsibilities outside work/Carers
My working environment protects women from violence/harassment/assault	Women travelling with dependents
	Women who are parents/have children

Table 3. Profiles of women more unsatisfied with the most relevant factors in women as employees

For more detail on the applied approach see Appendix 5.

Recommendations taking as a reference the maturity model

Main factors and recommendations for women in autonomous vehicles.

As in the other research areas of the DIAMOND project, to model and to present the results we have used the women Fairness and Inclusiveness Maturity Model developed in the DIAMOND project. Maturity Models are tools, used in different fields, to measure the ability of an organization for continuous improvement in a particular discipline. The higher the maturity, the higher will be the chances that incidents or errors will lead to improvements either in the quality or in the use of the resources of the discipline as implemented by the organization. The model consists of four increasing inclusiveness levels around three main topics: (1) capacity to meet required needs, (2) accessibility and (3) safety and security. For each topic we may include different issues as the following table 4 shows.

In terms of needs the importance of the NDRT will be notorious while applying a gender view would imply to pay attention to care mobility and defining trip-chaining related functionalities. Concerning accessibility, in addition to affordability which has a strong gender bias and attention to functional diversity, the implementation of shared vehicles will imply the introduction of a nomadic user concept with their unique features. This will imply an increasing importance of the flexibility of the layout of the vehicle. In safety and security, to the traditional concept of safety we need to add the need of trust to the system, being women more reluctant to give power to the vehicle, the key elements to remedy this situation may be proper training and communication between the vehicle and the passenger.

Of course, being AVs a field still under development and with a high degree of uncertainty, there are a variety the recommendations, some being more specific and other more focused on raising the awareness of the importance of women fairness

Capacity to meet the required needs	Accessibility	Safe and secure
Confidence & disengagement for NDRT	Extremely flexible for a nomadic user	Ergonomics / Biomechanics safety
Interaction between passengers	Children friendly	Communication management to generate trust
Comfort in Non-Driving Related Tasks (NDRT)	Women ergonomics	
Travel time Trip-chaining	Gender and intersectional factors	Control management to generate trust
Social Benefits	Inclusive design Disability	

Table 4. Issues in Capacity to meet the required needs, Accessibility, Safety and Security

solutions in AVs. Table 5 details the most important issues and needs identified and offers a group of recommendations.

Issues highlighted/ needs	Recommendation
CAPACITY TO MEET THE REQUIRED NEEDS	
Confidence & disengagement for NDRT	<p>When the level of confidence and trust in the AVs increases is easier for the 'drivers' to perform NDRT as they feel comfortable disengaging themselves from the driving issues. AVs should be designed to facilitate the disengagement from driving issues to allow NDRT.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 'Drivers' may disengage from the driving tasks with a minimum supervision and feel confident when conducting other tasks while the AV keeps control. • 'Drivers' needs to feel confident when conducting other tasks and specific automated functions are incorporated for this purpose such as strategies to avoid motion sickness, adaptation of the driving mode for different NDRT...
Interaction between passengers	<p>Interior layout and seating design solutions should provide different configurations to allow different degrees of interaction between passengers, from a more private or individual space to a more common space to promote the interaction between passengers, including caring tasks (e.g. children).</p> <p>The interior layout and seating solution should provide the possibility of different configurations addressing the desired degree of interaction with other passengers, from a set of private and individual spaces to a common space to facilitate interaction and care of other passengers.</p>
Comfort in NDRT	<p>NDRT must be performed comfortably by passengers or drivers. For this purpose, interior and ambient comfort facilities must be designed according with the needs of the different tasks identified.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific features must be incorporated to facilitate different types of tasks (e.g. adaptation of the illumination and auxiliary surfaces). • The interior layout should be easily reconfigurable for different task and postures (e.g. adaptable sitting and auxiliary surfaces, ambient comfort adaptable to the task, electronic facilities for working or entertainment...).
Travel time Trip-Chaining	<p>Considering travel time from a gender perspective implies considering the different mobility patterns, one specific characteristic of women displacement is the connection of different displacements more complex than men (e.g. dropping the kids in the school before going to the work).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAV should incorporate features to save time to destination, facilitate trip chaining (chained displacements) and other specific functions that may be related to the differentiated pattern of mobility of women. • CAVs should offer options (driving mode, green wave options...) to improve travel time in case of need. Automated driving function and not driving functions should be incorporated focused on chained displacements (e.g. car parking or waiting functions, planning complete route and task -list...).

Issues highlighted/ needs	Recommendation
Social Benefits	<p>A driving behaviour with low ecologic impact, respectful with other road users and contributing to the improvement of traffic flow is beneficial to the community.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The HMI should incorporate properly the communication and control of social benefits of the AV. • Social benefits must be communicated and perceived by occupants with proper indicators. Ideally, occupants are informed continuously by the system on social benefits allowing them to take informed decisions when selecting the automatic driving parameters (info for decision making). (e.g. by selecting this driving mode your car reduces 30% of energy consumption and it is a 10% more the respectful with pedestrians).
ACCESSIBILITY	
Extremely flexible for a nomadic user	<p>Guidelines: Some studies see the development of the AVs and their use to the development of a Sharing Service, that would imply a new concept of using the car with nomad passengers. Thus, flexibility in CAV design should be incorporated considering that 'The user of the car is a nomad traveler with their own luggage'.</p> <p>Cabin design should be flexible offering for example different support spaces/ surfaces allowing different configurations, open spaces fewer specific gadgets, flat surfaces, free from corners and bumps and easy to put and secure the luggage, and belongings and easy to clean.</p>
Children friendly	<p>The mobility of care, mainly performed by women, implies the displacement with children. CAV cabin should be a children friendly environment.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children safety aspect should be addressed from babies to teenagers. The AV should incorporate seats that may transform into busters for some sizes. For achieving a Children friendly design. children should be considered as a passenger with particular needs i.e. Design of the space to be comfortable for children behaviour and for the carer of the children for caring, monitoring and interacting with children.
Women ergonomics	<p>Women and men are different considering physical and physiological characteristics. CAV design should consider to women specific physical and physiological characteristics.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women ergonomics must be applied in design such as anthropometrics, reaches, forces and consider women variability and pregnancy. • Women further anatomical and physiological differences between women and men such as temperature perception (for thermal comfort), voice pitch (for HMI), typical postures (for interior layout), proprioceptors (vehicle dynamics) and systems works as fully for women as they do for men.

Issues highlighted/ needs	Recommendation
Gender and intersectional factors	<p>In addition to the physical and physiological differences CAV should consider gender factors for a fair design.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender differences must be explored to study different patterns of use for defining product users' needs and in design solutions. • Gender and other related intersectional variables should be identified and considered to establish a proper user centred design process and validation ensuring any disadvantage in the identified groups. CAV HMI provides a Gender-Neutral Conversation.
Inclusive design Disability	<p>The users of the AV are a varied group, with different needs and requirements. CAV design should consider the variability in the population needs and physical and physiological characteristics.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAV Design has to follow the principles of design for all. • CAV must incorporate specific features to facilitate the use by population with special needs including different types of functional diversity.
SAFE AND SECURE	
Ergonomics / Biomechanics safety	<p>Traditionally, with few exceptions, the car industry has only considered male models for designing the safety systems of the car. CAV safety systems must be fair with women.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety standards and design must consider anatomic (different breast sizes, ...) and physiologic differences (e.g. voice pitch, vision field) between men and women. • Safety standards and design should be based on women fair data bases considering all sizes and including pregnancy. • CAVs safety should be designed considering different women uses and environments (e.g. trip chaining, mobility of care) and further physiological differences such as driving styles, reaction times, preferences, stress and workload levels.
Communication management to generate trust	<p>An appropriate communication between the AVs and the passengers or drivers may impact highly in the trust and satisfaction of the whole system. Thus, CAV communication with the 'driver' is adapted to the user preference, profile and context.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 'Drivers' should be able to configure the amount and complexity of the received information according to the situation or their characteristics. • The HMI should provide automatic adaptation to the amount and complexity of information according to the experience, preference, task, trust, context to not overwhelm the 'driver' and be able to evolve over the time according to trust improvement and experience gained with the vehicle.

Issues highlighted/ needs	Recommendation
Control management to generate trust	<p>The previous experience of the drivers with advanced control systems, or their preferences (e.g. like to have everything under control) conditionate the preferences for the interaction with the AVs concerning the control issues. Thus, CAV 'driver' control and supervision must adapted to the user preference, profile and context.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 'Drivers' should configure the control and supervision level according to the situation (context) or their characteristics. • Ideally, the HMI should conform automatically the control and supervision level according to the experience, preference, task, trust, context and evolve over the time according to trust improvement and experience gained using the vehicle.

Table 5. Highlighted issues and appropriate recommendations

For more detail on this see Appendix 6

In Summary

We believe it could be encouraged at corporate and policy level for organization providing public transport service to assess and address their inclusivity and level of fairness in the scope of service provision offered. And a good way to do so is by benchmarking in a standardised way a fairness maturity level reached in various areas.

The areas we were able to directly assess in the scope of the project and for which we piloted a self-assessment tool were in the space of provision of surface public transport, provision of bike sharing service, employment in transport and a future oriented study towards future provision of autonomous vehicles services. The example of the self-assessment tools questions developed, and recommendations proposed can be seen at: <https://diamond-project.eu/deliverables/> and in <https://toolkit4fairness.eu>

11. Women versus Men

This ANOVA analysis was also conducted for the socio-demographic characteristic 'gender', identifying significant differences in the satisfaction with the transport system between Women and Men (Deliverable 4.3 DIAMOND). Results are shown below:

USE CASE 1

The analysis showed that the following factors have significant differences between women and men in the use case 1. In addition, in Table 3, there are also highlighted if men or women were more unsatisfied.

Key Factor for Women	Gender most unsatisfied with the Factor
Adequate personal space, layout of seating and appropriate ventilation and air conditioning	Men regarding the adequate personal space
	Women regarding the ventilation air conditioning
Intermodal options and connections. Including integration with alternative shared mobility services (e.g. bike, scooter and car sharing).	Women
Safety and harassment reporting points	Men
Visibility of the surrounding area	Women
Availability of appropriate services/facilities within the transport infrastructure (seating area, bar, pharmacy, ATMs...).	Men
Reliability of the service modes available in terms of time, price and security	Men

Table 3. Gender analysis about the satisfaction level with the most relevant factors in Railways

USE CASE 2

In this use case, the satisfaction level between women and men has not shown significant differences for any key factor.

USE CASE 3

In the bike sharing services, the analysis determined that the only factor with significant difference for gender is 'facilities at docking stations'. For it, women are less satisfied than men regarding this topic.

USE CASE 4

In this use case, the satisfaction level between women and men for all key factors has not shown any difference.

12. Foreseeing the future

Futuristic scenarios were presented in the Use case 1 (Hyperloop), Use case 2 (autonomous driving level 4+ and 5) and Use case 4 (Drones logistics), and analysed through the DAD survey and the AHP.A new list of key factors and relevance were obtained for the future (Deliverable 4.3 DIAMOND). No futuristic scenarios were foreseen for the Use case 3 (bike-sharing), so it is out of this futuristic analysis. Details of this analysis for use cases 1, 2 and 4 are shown below:

USE CASE 1

Table 4 indicates the key factors and its relevance in the Hyperloop scenario.

Use case 1 - Hyperloop	Relevance
Adequate personal space, layout of seating and appropriate ventilation and air conditioning.	18.91%
Walking time from stations to the points of interest.	14.82%
Intermodal options and connections.	13.78%
Safety and harassment reporting points	13.29%
Availability of appropriate services/ facilities within the transport infrastructure (seating area, bar, pharmacy, ATMs...).	13.26%
Visibility of the surrounding area	13.21%
Reliability of the service modes available in terms of time, price and security.	12.74%

Table 4. Key factors and its relevance for the Hyperloop future scenario

Depicted in a sectorial graph (Figure 5):

Figure 5 Sectorial graph with the distribution of the relevance between the key factors for the railway stations in the future (Hyperloop)

USE CASE 2

Table 5 indicates the key factors and its relevance in the fully automated vehicles scenario.

Use case 2 - Fully automated vehicles	Relevance
Perception of using a vehicle	27.67%
Perception of safety	26.89%
Health: people feeling (e.g. calm, stressed) when driving without steering wheel	25.74%
Be able to perform simultaneous tasks in driving environment	19.70%
Perception of need of training before using an AV	0.00%
Perception of boredom vs joy	15.23%

Table 5. Key factors and its relevance for the fully automated vehicles future scenario

Depicted in a sectorial graph (Figure 6):

Figure 6 Sectorial graph with the distribution of the relevance between the key factors for the autonomous vehicles in the future (fully automated vehicles)

USE CASE 4

Table 6 indicates the key factors and its relevance in the Drone logistics scenario.

Use case IV.- Drone logistics	Relevance
Gender equality communication policies	23.78%
Family friendly policies	24.17%
Security staff available	13.89%
Diversity training	13.63%
Gender pay equality	12.45%
Equality gender in promotions and recruitments	12.09%

Table 6. Key factors and its relevance for the Drone logistics future scenario

Depicted in a sectorial graph (Figure 7):

Figure 7 Sectorial graph with the distribution of the relevance between the key factors for the employment in the future (Drone logistics)

APPENDIX I

Philosophers have been trying to deal with issues of fairness for millennia, so we are not seeking a philosophical definition, but rather focus on a general pragmatic concept of fairness that was useful in the project^[iii]. Fairness can be a vague and ambiguous concept which evolves and changes over time and space and can be based on individual subjective reasoning and experiences, making any attempt at producing a universal definition a difficult process. The DIAMOND project, however, seeks to set out a practical definition of 'fairness' which can be applied to each use case as a framework; and importantly as an additional tool to help partners decide what data will be required in order to answer the relevant research question(s) and measure fairness. So the project definition of fairness remains focused on key, high level concepts of fairness, but is flexible enough to suit the users of transport, women employees in transport and the algorithms used, whilst still being easily understandable by all (participants, partners etc.) involved in the project.

DIAMOND Definition of Fairness

Women generally, and different groups of women specifically, can have complex mobility patterns in comparison to men e.g., mothers and older women report taking shorter commuting times but more journeys than men (McQuaid and Chen 2012; Madariaga 2013; Houston and Tilley 2016; Hanson 2010). It is also claimed that current transport systems do not always take these gendered differences into account when either planning or delivering services. Additionally, for many women driving private vehicles or using public transport modelled on the general physicality of men has also created issues with regards to seating, posture and the seatbelt safety; while self-driving cars may use algorithms based on databases which reflect past biases in car use rather than fairness across the potential population of users (for a full view of discussion see Deliverable 2.2 of DIAMOND).

Fairness can be a vague and somewhat ambiguous concept which can evolve and change over time and space and can be based on individual subjective reasoning and experiences. This makes any attempt at producing a universal definition a difficult process. The terms 'fairness' and 'justice' tend to be used to describe both how decisions are made and how individuals are treated within a community. Throughout the wider literature the notion of fairness is closely related to the concepts of **justice, equity and human rights**. Hence fairness needs to reflect access or opportunity to safely use the transport system, but also the distribution of benefits across the transport system.

For both Litman (2018) and Gullo et al. (2008) fairness in relation to transport mainly relates to equality of opportunity as without adequate transport, access to education or employment is difficult, which further impacts income equality. Litman (2018) separates the concept of equity into two separate types, horizontal which relates to the egalitarian concept of equal treatment of equals and vertical equity which is related to social justice and social inclusion and focuses on the difference (in ability or need) between and within groups, i.e., transport policies which favour disadvantaged groups such as people with disabilities.

Lee, Sener and Jones (2017) introduce five separate types of equity, which they argue are related specifically to fairness with regards to public use of and access to public transport.

- **Social equity** – analysis of social groups and is measured using variables based on income, race, sex and age, sexual identity and/or orientation, etc.
- **Spatial equity** – is a geographical level of analysis which looks to examine where the inequality is taking place, this is important in relation to transport policy planning 'because the effects of public policies tend to cluster around specific physical locations' (p. 213).
- **Procedural equity** – is associated with equity in the policy making process as opposed to the outcome of policy, in the case of transport policy planning procedural equity is related to having fair and equal evaluations included in the policy making decision.

- **Modal equity** – is related to ensuring that there is safe access for all groups to the range of local transport modes, the example provided is that ‘because walking and bicycling have higher mortality rates from vehicle accidents than driving, modal equity strategies would seek to restrict driving in order to slow or reduce vehicle traffic’ (p. 215)^[1] And that this range of transport is interconnected (multimodal journeys).
- **Distribution equity** – is linked to how transportation costs and benefits are distributed across society, currently this is evaluated for fairness by examining the accessibility to transport infrastructures which excludes any evaluation of how safely and easily people can travel to and from the station at all time.

All data collection activities have been conducted once ethical approval has been granted locally and by following a rigid ethical framework of conducting social research.

APPENDIX 2

Research Methods

Overall, the research has taken a mixed methods approach where both quantitative and qualitative methods, and various types of qualitative and quantitative approaches, have been integrated where possible (for a fuller description of methods used see DIAMOND Deliverable 4.1 section 2). This recognises that there are strengths and weaknesses with every method, but we have sought to build on complementary strengths and avoid overlapping weaknesses of the different methods used (Danzin, 2012; Creswell and Creswell, 2018).

Mixed methods approach has helped triangulate our results, i.e., combining different insights from different approaches (and expanding our understanding of findings by combining different approaches) and so increasing the rigour and confidence in our findings when they are supported or convergent validated by other methods.

The mixed methods used was both sequential (qualitative focus groups helped identify issues that were considered in the quantitative analysis (e.g., on the fairness characteristics) and then qualitative webinars were used to explore some of the quantitative results. Also, the quantitative and qualitative methods were used in parallel as the key Research Questions were explored in parallel, using different approaches.

The descriptive results are brought together in D4.2, with in-depth quantitative analysis presented in D4.3 and the main results integrated in D4.4. However, to avoid excessive duplication and to ensure the coherence of the results in D4.3, we do not repeat the full descriptive quantitative results in the current deliverable.

APPENDIX 3

Structured Open Data - Structured data refers to any data that resides in a fixed field within a record or file. This includes data contained in relational databases and spreadsheets. Some sources to obtain this type of quantitative information are official data bases like EUROSTAT, National Ministry of Transportation, National Railway Companies, ELTIS, etc. but also service providers which are part of DIAMOND consortium.

Structured Proprietary Data

Observations - From a general point of view, observations consist of a collection of methods based on counting the presence and localization of an object within the observed area (Use Case I and III) or by observing users' behaviour through cameras and sensors (Use Case II). Observations provide data applicable for the Use Case I, II, and III. Observations for Use Case I and III focus on relevant features of transportation settings related to railway and bike sharing stations respectively.

User Satisfaction Questionnaires

online - Users and employees' satisfaction index questionnaire is a tool commonly used by public transport service companies, such as railway companies, in order to evaluate their services and make improvements. Satisfaction has shown itself to be elusive to measurement and very service specific — making it a rather less meaningful indicator when aggregated. It can only be interpreted in relation to the significance of a given service and responses are easily swayed by the broader public mood.

Social Media Data

Dynamic Argumentative Analysis

Online Focus Groups - his kind of research involves organised discussion with a selected group of individuals to gain information about their views and experiences of a subject of study. They are particularly useful for obtaining several perspectives about the same topic gaining insights into people's shared understandings of everyday life and the ways in which individuals are influenced by others in a group situation.

Online One to One Interviews

Literature Review - Literature review is a critical analysis of published sources on a particular topic. It is an assessment of the literature and provides a summary, classification, comparison and evaluation.

APPENDIX 4

Foreseeing the future

Futuristic scenarios were presented in the Use case 1 (Hyperloop), Use case 2 (autonomous driving level 4+ and 5) and Use case 4 (Drones logistics), and analysed through the DAD survey and the AHP. A new list of key factors and relevance were obtained for the future (Deliverable 4.3 DIAMOND). No futuristic scenarios were foreseen for the Use case 3 (bike-sharing), so it is out of this futuristic analysis. Details of this analysis for use cases 1, 2 and 4 are shown below:

Public Transport users

The future scenario of the Use Case 1 was chosen based on the document published by the European Commission 'New Horizons: Data from a Delphi Survey in Support of European Union Future Policies in Research and Innovation' (European Commission 2017) in which new technologies were based on the hyperloop as a future scenario of the railways system.

Table 4 indicates the key factors and its relevance in the Hyperloop scenario.

Use case 1 - Hyperloop	Relevance
Adequate personal space, layout of seating and appropriate ventilation and air conditioning.	18.91%
Walking time from stations to the points of interest.	14.82%
Intermodal options and connections.	13.78%
Safety and harassment reporting points	13.29%
Availability of appropriate services/facilities within the transport infrastructure (seating area, bar, pharmacy, ATMs...).	13.26%
Visibility of the surrounding area	13.21%
Reliability of the service modes available in terms of time, price and security.	12.74%

Table 4. Key factors and its relevance for the Hyperloop future scenario

Autonomous driving

NHTSA (National Highway Traffic Safety Administration) and SAE (Society of Automotive Engineering) classifies the level of automatization according to Figure 1. Basically the levels of vehicle automation range from driver-assist technologies (e.g., lane keeping, parking assist, etc.) to full vehicle automation, in which the vehicle is responsible for all safety-critical functions (Olsen and Sweet, 2019). The dotted line highlights the technological leap existing between L3 and L4 and plus.

Figure 6. Summary of the different levels of automation (Figure from IBV based on NHSTA)

Autonomous Driving of DIAMOND project focuses on the study of self-owned L4+ vehicle in the present scenario and above it in the future scenario. L4+ vehicles imply a disruption with actual vehicle technology. This disruption comes with the disappearance of the driver of the car as we understand it today. Lower automation levels of the vehicles, L2 and L3, still require the driver to take control of the steering wheel if required, while that ability to take-over is not required for L4+ (Collet and Musicant, 2019).

Table 5 indicates the key factors and its relevance in the fully automated vehicles scenario.

Use case 2 - Fully automated vehicles	Relevance
Perception of using a vehicle	27.67%
Perception of safety	26.89%
Health: people feeling (e.g. calm, stressed) when driving without steering wheel	25.74%
Be able to perform simultaneous tasks in driving environment	19.70%
Perception of need of training before using an AV	0.00%
Perception of boredom vs joy	15.23%

Table 5. Key factors and its relevance for the fully automated vehicles future scenario

Women as Employees

Vertex 6 of employment in the future scenario was focused on 'Drone traffic logistics as an important economic sector employing 1.5% of the total EU workforce (including maintenance experts, service, 'drivers', packaging etc.)' based on the document published by the European Commission 'New Horizons: Data from a Delphi Survey in Support of European Union Future Policies in Research and Innovation' (European Commission 2017).

Table 6 indicates the key factors and its relevance in the Drone logistics scenario.

Use case IV.- Drone logistics	Relevance
Gender equality communication policies	23.78%
Family friendly policies	24.17%
Security staff available	13.89%
Diversity training	13.63%
Gender pay equality	12.45%
Equality gender in promotions and recruitments	12.09%

Table 6. Key factors and its relevance for the Drone logistics future scenario

^[1] Impact is based on the Effectiveness about how the implementation of each recommendation will affect the improvement of all Key factors (Top 10 Factors) and also based on the cost of implementing this recommendation (Efficiency). This was estimated through a Bayesian Network analysis for the Effectiveness calculation and expert knowledge for the estimation of the costs. See D7.3 of DIAMOND for more details.

^[2] This analysis was based on an ANOVA test capable to identify significant statistical differences regarding the satisfaction showed by users and employees per each socio-demographic characteristic.

Recommendations were generated, and later validated, in a bottom-up approach in workshops and surveys.

- The recommendations generated for Top 10 FC for all the UCs took into consideration the ANOVA analysis by addressing the specific women profiles most unsatisfied. Moreover, 16 experts' attendees to UC-I session, 13 experts' attendees to UC-II session, 9 experts' attendees to UC-III session and 8 experts' attendees to UC-IV session validated them in the workshop that took place on July 21st 2021.
- The recommendations generated for the rest of FC were address to women as a homogeneous group and validated through an online survey. A Fairness Measure was considered validated if at least the 80% of the respondents considered appropriate the recommendation. 18 respondents validated recommendations in UC-I, 10 respondents validated recommendations in UC-II, 10 respondents validated recommendations in UC-III and 10 respondents validated recommendations in UC-IV.

APPENDIX 5

Recommendations on making transport use and employment more appropriate and friendly for women

The research applied a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative research methods, comprising a comprehensive literature review, DAD surveys, online surveys, interviews, user satisfaction surveys and focus group discussions (Gorriani et al., 2019; and García-jiménez et al., 2020). The list of the most relevant Fairness Characteristics (FCs) or women needs was obtained from the quantitative data analysis (AHP and machine learning techniques) and from the qualitative data analysis (through the interdisciplinary analysis, Focus groups and semi-structured interviews). The most relevant Fairness Characteristics were weighted and hierarchised using the AHP (Poveda-Reyes et al., 2021) and Bayesian Network analysis (Molero et al., 2021).

After determining the main needs and barriers women face, the Top 10 Fairness Characteristics were ranked for each use case (using ANOVA analysis). The aim was to define if there are significant differences for the characteristics/profiles of the person with the various characteristics set out in the model - polyhedral individual (PI) and also set which specific profiles were the lowest satisfied according to the UESI responses.

Finally, the recommendations were set. To do so, an interdisciplinary panel made of experts provided the recommendations:

1. The recommendations generated for **Top 10 Fairness** Characteristics for all the UCs took into consideration the ANOVA analysis by addressing the **specific women profiles most unsatisfied**. Moreover, experts' attendees to **workshop validate them** (16 attendees to UC-I session, 13 attendees to UC-II session, 9 attendees to UC-III session and 8 attendees to UC-IV session).
2. The recommendations generated for **the rest of Fairness** Characteristics were address to **women as a homogeneous group** and **validated through an online survey**. A Fairness Measure (upon which the recommendations are largely based) was considered validated if at least the 80% of the respondents considered appropriate the recommendation and more than 5 respondents participated in the survey.

The most relevant Top 10 Fairness Characteristics identified through the quantitative and the qualitative analysis as well as the recommendations by experts to address these FCs, are summarised in the tables below for each Use Case.

APPENDIX 6

Autonomous Vehicles

Analysis of Social Media

DIAMOND project investigated gender differences in social media through a content analysis of hashtags and relevant keywords of the activity of Twitter users. About 1 million of Tweets in total, from December 2019 to October 2020, across partner countries were collected in order to provide more robust cross-cultural findings.

The analysis of activity in this social network about AVs found that **women are more concerned with social impact, social context and feelings while men tend to focus more on aspects related to technology and business**. Women tend to use more negative language, using fewer positive words related to business and innovation and a more negative tone. Positive words that women did use tended to be in relation to social and daily life.

Top factors affecting acceptance of autonomous vehicles

DIAMOND project identified and defined a set of factors affecting and determining women's acceptance of autonomous vehicles. These factors or Fairness Characteristics (FCs) were classified in a 3-level hierarchy, being the labels of the top level: (1) safety & security, (2) comfort, (3) mobility, (4) economy, (5) environment and (6) design options. A Bayesian Network analysis was performed to rank and weight all the level 3 FCs for women. After merging them with the results of the survey and simulation experiment, the summary reads as follows:

- **Non-Driving Related Tasks (NDRT).** Four level 3 FCs were related with the possibility of performing NDRT as full attention of the driver is no more required in L4+ AVs. They included comfort and perception of boredom/joy when performing these activities and the degree of interaction with other passengers (including taking care of dependent people).
- **Social benefits.** Two level 3 FCs highlighted the importance of social benefits. The most important being the optimization of the well-being of other road users including pedestrians or cyclists. The potential reduction of the ecological impact was the other factor.
- **Acceptability.** One level 3 FCs was under this concept, mainly linked to the technology, considering aspects such as the degree of agreement/satisfaction on driving a car without steering wheel.
- **Trust and need of control.** Two level 3 FCs were under these two related concepts. They incorporated concepts such as the degree of trust when driving under different weather conditions and the importance of controlling driving variables (such as speed), rating women higher than men the importance of control.
- **Seize the time.** One level 3 FC was under this concept. It integrates the concept of different driving modes (urgent/comfort) and it may be related to the need of using the time wisely. Making the most of the time was rated higher by women.

Main differences between men and women when evaluating feelings and needs in Automated Driving Vehicles

The main goal of DIAMOND in the autonomous vehicles field was the identification of gender-driven needs, preferences and stressors related to autonomous driving experience to transform them into indications and recommendations for friendlier autonomous vehicles. For this purpose, experiments took place in IBV's Human Autonomous Vehicle (HAV), a dynamic driving simulator enabling the emulation of different degrees of autonomy, dynamical behaviors as well as monitoring and detecting the emotions of the passengers (Belda-Lois et al., 2020). The use of the HAV was combined with questionnaires to measure the subjective opinion of the passengers after the experiment.

Figure 7: Physiological measures in HAV simulator

The following lines describe the main differences identified, grouped under the following tags: (1) differentiated patterns of mobility, (2) Non-Driving Related Tasks (NDRT), (3) social benefits, (4) safety and security, (5) acceptability, (6) trust and need of control and (7) seize the time.

I. Differentiated patterns of mobility.

Women and men have different patterns of mobility as we have seen in the different areas of study of the DIAMOND project. Between the participants in the experimentation we found that 50% of women trip chained at least once a week, while only 25% of men did. This is consistent with the results of the bibliographic review, being trip chaining clearly identified with a gender bias. What we found was that the factor 'with/without children' were not significant in trip chaining frequency, meaning that men with children do not change they 'standard' pattern.

When considering different mobility purposes, we have observed similar results between genders. However, the frequency of the displacements related to 'own leisure activities' is higher for participants without children and 'accompanying my family to their leisure activities' is higher for participant with children.

2. **NDRT – Seize the time.** Although the perception of the capability to perform NDRT in an AV is similar and high for men and women, women show a higher interest in performing them than men. This result is more significant for women with children. Regarding work during displacement, **women are more interested in working during displacement** than men we have attributed this to the need of seize the time.

Having children increased the interest in performing activities 'to care for other passengers' for women and men. However, children's needs are a priority only for women, notably for the group of women with children (80%) for whom this is their first priority.

When analyzing the emotions experienced when performing NDRT men present the highest activation level compared to the other scenarios and also comparing with women. This fact could be attributed to a higher cognitive effort of men while performing a simultaneous task.

3. **Social benefits.** Autonomous vehicles need criteria to 'decide' their behaviour, criteria to drive. These 'criteria', also known as Operational Design Domain (ODD), may combine different rules. According to our results all groups agreed that the most important criterion was the optimization of wellbeing of other road users. However, the importance score for **optimization of energy efficiency** differed clearly, here **women scored the importance of this criterion much higher.**

4. **Safety and security.** Regarding **safety aspects**, the perceived **reduction of accident rate** with AVs is similar for all groups. However, in the statement '**AVs are safer than conventional cars under any conditions**', the agreement is close to neutrality and in this case, women **score it lower, showing a slight disagreement.** This could be a consequence of a long experience with vehicles not attending specific and basic needs of women (basic ergonomics, safety of pregnant women...).

5. **Acceptability.** Although in our study we did not find differences by gender, when asking about the willingness to buy an AV before the experiment we found differences between women and men. Women disagreed while men assigned a neutral score. After the simulation experience, gender is not significant anymore but the factor 'with/without children' becomes significant. Women with children, that before the experiment expressed no interest in purchasing an AV, after the were the group with the highest agreement with the statement

6. **Trust and need of control.** Women gave a higher importance to keep control of the driving features of the AVs.

7. **Seize the time.** Making the most of the time was rated higher by women and in relation to the AVs may signify to prefer urgent driving mode to reduce the time required to reach the destination point or to have the opportunity of performing other tasks during this displacement. When simulating the urgent driving mode, the arousal level was higher than with comfort driving mode. The arousal difference between both driving configurations were notoriously higher for men. Men, in the comfort scenario, are significantly less activated (lower arousal) than in the rest of scenarios and, also compared with women. Thus, we find a clear 'relaxing' effect of the comfort scenario for men, while we do not find it for women, for whom the comfort scenario has the same arousal level as others scenarios.

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